

Support for Pro-Indigenous Policies Amid Conflict

The Case of the Mapuche in Chile

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1 Introduction

In the last decade, the southern regions of Chile have witnessed increased violence in the conflict between the State and the indigenous Mapuche people (Carlin et al., 2022; Fernández and Fuentes, 2018). The Mapuche are the most populous indigenous group in Chile. They represent about 10 % of the total population. The Mapuche seek ancestral land restitution, economic reparations, cultural recognition, and territorial autonomy. Since colonial times, they have suffered from high rates of poverty, land-rights infringements, and cultural suppression (Crow, 2013; Haughney, 2006). The Mapuche criticize current public policies to redress these inequalities as insufficient. Some pursue peaceful tactics to demand public policies from the State. A minority participates in violent strategies, such as arson attacks and forcible land occupations. In May 2022, Chile declared a state of emergency in its southern provinces to allow the armed forces to deal with “violence and disorder.” Since then, the state of emergency has been renewed at least 33 times.

The literature frequently identifies that nonviolent campaigns are more effective than violent ones in achieving their goals (Arves, Cunningham and McCulloch, 2019; Feinberg, Willer and Kovacheff, 2020; Huff and Kruszewska, 2016; Muñoz and Anduiza, 2019; Simpson, Willer and Feinberg, 2018). Violence reduces support for social movements as it alienates potential allies and sympathizers. Yet, nonviolent mobilization from minority groups face additional obstacles due to widespread biases. Manekin and Mitts (2022) find that nonviolence only increases success for dominant groups. Majority groups perceive ethnic minorities resisting nonviolently as more violent than dominant groups, decreasing their chances of success.

Existing studies in the social movements and movement tactics literature implicitly assume identification with ethnic groups is fixed, stable, and unique. In-group identification is considered to precede political attitudes and violence. However, a considerable body of scholarship shows that identification with ethnic groups is often fluid and can change due to political and economic events (Chandra, 2012; Cornell and Hartmann, 2006). Individuals can also hold multiple group identifications simultaneously. The following questions then arise: Is the relationship between political violence and support for a minority social movement’s goals mediated by changes in self-reported ethnic identification? For the minority

group, does political violence by the group diminish ethnic identification with it and, in turn, reduce support for the group's goals?

2 Conflict and Group Identification

Previous studies find some heterogeneity in reactions to violence. Muñoz and Anduiza (2019) find heterogeneity based on previous support for the movement. When exposed to violence, the movement's core supporters reduce their support to a lesser extent than weak supporters, opposed, and non-aligned citizens. Manekin and Mitts (2022) find heterogeneity according to the ethnicity of the respondent and the protester. They argue that nonviolence only increases success for dominant groups. In the US, White respondents perceive African American engaging in peaceful protest as more violent than White protesters. In Israel, Ethiopian and Arab Israelis are perceived as more violent than the white Jewish majority when protesting peacefully.

Most studies implicitly assume identification with ethnic groups is fixed, stable, and unique. However, constructivist scholarship shows that identification with an ethnic group is fluid, can change, and is the result of political processes. Along these lines, in-group identifications not only shape reactions to violence, but they are molded by violence.

This observation is relevant to many contexts, including in Latin America, where ethnic identification is fluid (Yashar, 2015). Against a backdrop of indigenous mobilization on a range of issues and the use of both violent and nonviolent tactics, indigenous identities are activated in some contexts and not others. Even in the United States, where ethnic categories have traditionally been considered more rigid, recent studies show that some Americans switch their Hispanic origin to align with their politics (Agadjanian and Lacy, 2021; Egan, 2020).

Shifting self-identification with an ethnic group is particularly possible when there is no single list of attributes that can solely define ethnicity with certainty. In Chile, which is where we conduct our study, there is no single list of attributes that can solely define ethnicity with certainty. Both subjective and objective factors are used to define the Mapuche ethnic identification. A factorial study by Mateo Piñones and Valenzuela Carvallo (2017) shows that Chileans employ different information to judge whether someone is a Mapuche: their parents' self-identification as Mapuche, interest in Mapuche traditions, a Mapuche last name, and skin color. The researchers did not find a difference in how Mapuche and non-Mapuche citizens evaluate Mapuche ethnicity.

This context makes identification with the Mapuche somewhat fluid. An individual may identify as Mapuche at home and not in school. A non-indigenous Chilean might identify as Chilean most of the time, but as "both Chilean and Mapuche" when given the option. Along these lines, a 2022 survey asked indigenous and non-indigenous Chileans whether they felt "Mapuche, Chilean, or both." Among subjects who consider themselves Mapuche, 45 percent said they felt "both Chilean and Mapuche". In 2006, only 28 percent had chosen this response. This suggests the Mapuche have become less likely to prioritize their Mapuche identity over others.

In this context, we argue that exposure to violent tactics by indigenous groups shapes self-identification and, consequently, support for pro-indigenous policies. In this project, we

focus on Mapuche individuals in the Macrozona Sur of Chile, where most rural Mapuche live and the conflict is most intense. We expect violent tactics to decrease identification with the Mapuche and diminish support for public policies like land restitution.

3 The Conflict Between the Mapuche and the Chilean State

The Mapuche constitute around 1.7 of the 18.3 million Chileans. About 35 % live in the urban Santiago area, and 45 % reside in the southern regions of Araucania, BioBio, Los Rios, and Los Lagos.

The current phase of the conflict started in 1990 with democratization. By 1990, Mapuche communities possessed titles for approximately 300,000 hectares of land, which was 40 percent less than the area designated to them between 1866 and 1929 (Haughney, 2006).¹ During this decade, the Mapuche protested against extractivist projects including logging, fishing, and the construction of hydroelectric power plants. They demanded the restitution of lands and the respect of land treaties from the 19th century (Fernández and Fuentes, 2018).

The conflict between the Chilean State and the Mapuche has turned increasingly violent.² Since 2010, the number of attacks, in which a group intends to damage other groups, or their property, has increased.³ The types of attack that have increased the most are arson and firearm attacks.⁴ Meanwhile, peaceful land invasions and demonstrations have increased to a lesser extent.⁵ State coercion against the Mapuche, defined as the use of state repression or legal coercion, has grown as well. The most common types of coercion are arrests and evictions.

¹After the Chilean state seized the Mapuche territory through a series of military campaigns and agreements between 1861 and 1883, the Mapuche were assigned collective land titles known as “títulos de merced” and were confined to areas called “reducciones” (reservations). Between 1866 and 1929, 2,918 títulos de merced were issued to the Mapuche, encompassing 510,386.67 hectares (Aylwin et al., 2003). Multiple pieces of legislation prohibited indigenous land from being sold to non-indigenous people, but indigenous land was still transferred to non-Mapuche through legal loopholes and illegal transactions.

²The Chilean Chamber of Deputies declared four Mapuche groups as terrorist organizations: Coordinator Arauco Malleco (CAM), the Weichan Auka Mapu (WAM), the Resistance Mapuche Malleco (RMM) and Resistance Mapuche Lavkenche (RML). See Proyecto de Resolución N° 135.

³MACEDA is a a micro-level dataset on the self-determination conflict between the Chilean State and the Mapuche, with data from 1990 to 2021 (Cayul et al., 2022). The database has 4529 events. An event is defined as a "set of actions occurring in the context of the conflict at a given place and time". The newspaper El Mercurio was the primary media source used to construct it. To minimize the over-reporting of violence and under-reporting of state repression in the conservative El Mercurio, the authors augmented this with alternative media sources. They used public communications from Mapuche organizations to complement and confirm the data obtained, but not to increase the number of events. They did this to minimize strategic self-reporting.

⁴In the dataset, attacks are always violent and include arson, bombing, and attacks with weapons.

⁵Land invasions are the seizing or occupation of land by the Mapuche. They are coded as violent if there is confrontation at the moment of invading. Otherwise, they are peaceful.

4 Survey Experiment

4.1 Experimental Design

The experiment consists of a vignette with a news report describing an event in the conflict between the Mapuche and the Chilean state. Mapuche respondents will be randomly assigned to one of two vignettes with simple random assignment: a peaceful Mapuche demonstration or an arson attack.

Immediately after exposure to the vignette, respondents will answer a series of mediator questions about their identification with the Mapuche. Then, they will be asked about their views on land restitution policies, their willingness to learn more about the history of Mapuche lands, the need for police intervention, and support for other pro-Mapuche policies. The survey will include an open-ended question to allow us to better understand the categorical response on land restitution.

4.2 Survey Details

We will use online panel Netquest, with an expected sample of at least 300 Mapuche respondents in the Macrozona Sur.^{6 7} We will include quotas for gender and socioeconomic level.

We will identify Mapuche respondents using a question on ethnicity drawn from the Chilean census. We will measure the following covariates pre-treatment: political interest, left-right ideology, presidential approval, number of Mapuche last names, and contact with Mapuche individuals. Netquest will provide variables with respondents' sex, age, education level, and socioeconomic level.⁸

We will include one pre-treatment attention check to discard inattentive participants.

4.3 Randomization and Treatments

The wording of the experimental treatments are as follows:

Next we would like you to read a brief news report. People sometimes mobilize to change policies. The report will describe one such episode. Please read it carefully. Afterwards, we will ask your opinion.

Respondents will be randomly assigned to one of two treatment conditions: 1 and 2.

1. Mapuche Demonstration in Temuco

In the Araucania, a region where there are popular Mapuche demands for

⁶The regions of Bio-Bio, Araucania, Los Lagos, and Los Rios, form the Macrozona Sur. This is where the majority of rural Mapuche live and where most of the conflict events happen.

⁷The exact sample size may be slightly smaller or larger than 300. We aim to collect the largest sample we can given constraints with recruitment.

⁸Netquest asks these sociodemographic variables every year to their panelists. Pre-treatment questions can be found in the Appendix.

ancestral land restitution, [Mapuche groups marched in the streets of the city center of Temuco](#) last weekend. This event happened amid the growing conflict between the Mapuche and the Chilean state. The number of [demonstrations](#) has increased in recent years.

A neighbor who lives near the area where the [demonstration](#) occurred reported that "[it was an orderly demonstration with many people. They marched towards the intendencia regional.](#)"

2. [Arson Attack by Mapuche Group in the Araucania](#)

In the Araucania, a region where there are popular Mapuche demands for ancestral land restitution, [a Mapuche group burned down five trucks and four houses in a rural area](#) last weekend. This event happened amid the growing conflict between the Mapuche and the Chilean state. The number of [arson attacks](#) has increased in recent years.

A neighbor who lives near the area where the [arson attack](#) occurred reported that "[a group of hooded individuals set the trucks and houses on fire. It took the firemen a long time to control the flames.](#)"

4.4 Mediator Questions

The mediator, ethnic identification with the Mapuche, is captured through three different questions: (i) self-identification, (ii) interest in Mapuche traditions, and (iii) participation in Mapuche ceremonies and events. These indicators are in line with those examined by Mateo Piñones and Valenzuela Carvallo (2017). Collectively, they are latent indicators of an underlying self identification with the Mapuche.

1. Do you feel Chilean, Mapuche, or a mix of both?
 - Chilean
 - Chilean first and Mapuche next
 - Chilean and Mapuche at the same time
 - Mapuche first and Chilean next
 - Mapuche
2. How interested are you in Mapuche traditions?
 - Very Interested
 - Somewhat Interested
 - Not Very Interested
 - Not Interested At All
3. How likely are you to participate in Mapuche ceremonies or events in the next year?

- Very Likely
- Likely
- Unlikely
- Very Unlikely

4.5 Outcome Measures and Expectations

We assess treatment effects on four groups of outcomes: support for land restitution, political learning, need for police action, and support for other pro-Mapuche public policies. Below we lay out our expectations and measures.

4.5.1 Land Restitution

Our main outcome questions measure support for land restitution. This is the most salient Mapuche policy demand and is mentioned in the vignette.

We expect the arson attack treatment to decrease support for land restitution by diminishing ethnic identification with the Mapuche.

We do not register particular expectations for the open-ended question, viewing this element as exploratory.

1. Since the mid-1990s, the government has purchased and allocated around 120,000 hectares of land to Mapuche communities that can prove prior dispossession from their territories. Do you oppose or support the government expanding its land restitution policy to Mapuche communities?
 - Strongly Oppose
 - Somewhat Oppose
 - Somewhat Support
 - Strongly Support
2. Considering that state resources are limited, on a scale of 1 to 10, where 1 means that “the resources should preferably be allocated to the restitution of lands for the Mapuche” and 10 means that “resources should preferably be allocated to education and health programs for all Chileans”, where would you place yourself?
3. You stated that the government [should not/should] strengthen its land restitution policy to the Mapuche. Could you please type a few sentences telling us how you view the Mapuche effort to reclaim ancestral land?

4.5.2 Political Learning

Previous literature mainly investigates how violence affects movement support, negotiation strategies, and perceptions of violence. However, there has been less exploration

of how violence impacts information seeking and learning about conflicts. Considering that informed and engaged citizens are crucial for a thriving democracy, this study also examines how violence affects information-seeking behavior. Political learning also moves a step beyond opinions of support or opposition, toward taking some concrete action.

Arson attacks may increase political learning because of increased interest in the conflict. On the other hand, arson attacks may decrease political learning because of decreased sympathy to the Mapuche.

We weakly anticipate that effects will be mediated by ethnic identification.

4. Would you like to read a short document about [\[demonstrations\]](#)[\[arson attacks\]](#) as they relate to the history of Mapuche lands in Chile? If you do, we will share the link with you at the end of this survey.
 - Yes
 - No

4.5.3 Police Action

In addition to policy support, and to benchmark our study against other recent findings in the literature, we examine how different tactics affect respondents' thoughts on the need for police action. For the Mapuche, we expect the arson attack treatment to increase the need for police action.

We weakly anticipate that effects will be mediated by ethnic identification.

5. To what extent do you believe that police action is required to address the [\[demonstrations\]](#)[\[arson attacks\]](#)? Indicate your response on a scale of 0 to 10, where 0 indicates not required at all and 10 indicates definitely required.

4.5.4 Other Public Policies

We also measure support for other public policies that benefit the Mapuche. These are not mentioned in the vignette. We expect less movement in these outcomes since they are not about land. Even so, movement demands are broader than land, and people may have an association between the Mapuche and these demands.

We expect the arson attack treatment to decrease support for pro-Mapuche public policies by diminishing ethnic identification with the Mapuche.

6. Please tell me if you strongly agree, agree, neither agree nor disagree, disagree, or strongly disagree with each of the following statements:
 - The government should offer monetary reparations to the Mapuche to compensate for prior dispossession

- The government should consult with the Mapuche about matters involving their territory
- The government should grant greater autonomy to Mapuche communities to govern their own affairs
- The Mapuche should have reserved seats in Congress in order to ensure adequate representation of their interests

5 Estimation Strategy

5.1 Mediation Effects

We will estimate the average causal mediation effect (ACME) to examine whether the treatment effect on the outcomes is mediated by ethnic identification. We will estimate the ACME via the “mediation” package in R. Relevant controls include sex, age, socioeconomic level, and left-right ideology. This follows the method proposed by Imai et al. (2011).

5.2 Average Treatment Effects

We will also estimate ordinary least squares regressions of the outcomes on a factor variable capturing the experimental condition, where the baseline category is the Mapuche demonstration. As our main measure, we will estimate regressions with robust standard errors without controls. Specifically, we will estimate the following equation for each of the outcomes:

$$Y_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{Treatment}_i + \epsilon_i$$

where Y_i is the relevant outcome measure for respondent i , Treatment_i is an indicator for the individual’s assignment to the treatment group, and ϵ_i is the error term.

For robustness, we will also estimate Lin regressions with pre-treatment covariates (Lin, 2013). The most relevant controls include sex, age, socioeconomic level, and left-right ideology.

6 Power Analysis

We include some power calculations below.

Figure 1: Power Calculations

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7 Appendix

7.1 Pre-Treatment Questions

1. Do you consider yourself to be a member of any indigenous or native people?
 - Yes
 - No
2. (If Q1=Yes) Which one?
 - Mapuche
 - Aymara
 - Rapa Nui
 - Lican Antai
 - Quechua
 - Colla
 - Diaguita
 - Kawesqar
 - Yagan or Yamana
 - Other
3. In general, how interested are you in politics?
 - Not interested at all
 - Not very interested
 - Somewhat interested
 - Very interested
4. Considering the two surnames of your father and the two surnames of your mother, how many of these 4 surnames have Mapuche origin?
 - None
 - One
 - Two
 - Three
 - Four
5. Now we are going to ask about people you may know, whether they are close (family or friends) or not. A person is known if you at least know their first name and you could talk to them if you met them on the street or somewhere. Thinking only about the people who live in Chile, can you tell me how many people you know are Mapuche?

- None
 - 1 to 5
 - 6 to 10
 - More than 10
6. Regardless of your political position, do you approve or disapprove of the way in which President Gabriel Boric is conducting his government?
- Disapprove a lot
 - Somewhat disapprove
 - Neither approve nor disapprove
 - Somewhat approve
 - Approve a lot
7. In politics, people normally speak of “left” and “right”. On a scale where 0 is left and 10 is right, where would you place yourself?
- 1-10 scale